

**EFFECTIVENESS OF APPLYING INDUCTIVE METHOD IN
TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGE**

Shakhnoza Turaeva

Tashkent State University of Uzbek language and
Literature named after Alisher Navai Uzbekistan,
Tashkent ,

shakhnozaturayeva@gmail.com

Annotation. This article reveals the features of using inductive and deductive methods of teaching a foreign language, gives a clear understanding of these terminologies. The issues of the effectiveness of using this technique are covered, its advantages and disadvantages are analyzed. The issue of developing critical thinking and self-knowledge among students when using this technology in their studies is revealed.

Key words: methods of teaching English, inductive method, deductive method, advantages and disadvantages of the inductive method.

Inductive teaching method in English World literature, and especially stories about great detectives, their analytical data, determination to achieve results and progress, understanding the behavior of others, disclosure of secret information, always attract the younger generation. Great and world-famous detective works of English classics such as Agatha Christie, Arthur Conan Doyle, stories about them motivate and interest, develop an interest in research and analytical activities, which allows you to pay attention to the use inductive methods of teaching English - inductive teaching [4]. Having analyzed the main advantages and disadvantages of this method in this work, it can safely be considered super effective. This method is often considered discovery learning, which is quite justified. At the center of the learning process lies a technique where the teacher presents specific examples to students and encourages them to discover or deduce a basic rule based on what they have them information [3]. In this

way, he motivates students to take part in the natural discovery exercise, which is always leads to the result of awareness and understanding. Using this method results in a change in roles between the teacher and a student [6].

Inductive and deductive teaching.

The concepts and the differences between the two popular approaches, such as how their concepts are often replaced with each other. Inductive learning is a process in which the teacher gives examples or gives models as a result to students determine or derive a rule independently, analyzing the available information and making a conclusion [5].

Deductive learning is the reverse side of inductive learning, where the teacher gives a specific rule, and the students try to apply this rule in your examples, texts and exercises, working them out with examples [3]. There is no universal method applying only one best approach or technique. The combination of these two methods may be more effective in depending on the purpose and objectives of the lesson. Let's consider the factors necessary when selection of these methods.

Using inductive teaching:

- Students have the skills of reasoning, analysis, there is obviously a desire to develop this, in this case learning is transmitted and is in the hands of the students, but is controlled and directed remotely by the teacher.
- A simple, consistent grammatical structure, rule, is taught, easy to understand.
- Students work better in pairs or small groups.
- In class there is time and space for exploration and discovery.
- Students are quite motivated and strive to learn new skills.
- The composition of the group of students is mainly young, because it is inductive learning is usually more interesting and favorable for the young and active [4].

Application of the deductive method training:

- The teacher's desire to create a group with a more uniform and identical level of language proficiency, because receive the same tools.

- Teaching a complex topic, grammar, which requires sufficient number of exceptions and features.
- Individual training or one-on-one training.
- Accuracy is of paramount importance in a particular case.
- Limited time to master the educational material.
- The group consists of adult students.

Analysis of inductive teaching methods.

Methodology using strategy self-knowledge and self-education is becoming increasingly popular throughout world, and its various forms are also developing, used in various spheres of education. Inductive teaching is part of this teaching strategy. Learning is transferred and placed in the hands of the learner, making it a highly effective tool for stimulating student participation and engagement. Long-term studies have shown that compared to the deductive method, inductive learning is more effective. It is especially important to note that inductive reasoning is fundamental force in the cognitive development of people in general [5].

Benefits of inductive learning:

- The educational process is very active, which helps to increase student motivation.
- The process of analysis contributes to the development of mental and analytical activity, which also has a good effect on the whole learning process.
- This technique involves more a holistic approach to learning a foreign language.
- Students experience a sense of achievement and personal satisfaction, which also motivates them to continue activities in this direction.

Disadvantages of the existing inductive method:

- Students' habit of deduction method of learning from previous experience training, as it is more traditional, which can cause difficulties when introducing and using other, innovative techniques of the inductive method.

- Wrong conclusions during selection topics or information, as well as the inability to make a qualitative analysis may lead to demotivation and disappointment among students.

- Takes longer.

- Differences between student levels may be obvious that as a consequence will lead to lack of confidence in your knowledge and cognitive abilities.

Essential Strategies for the teachers using Inductive method

A teacher using the inductive method must be modern, flexible and inquisitive, as well as attentive to the learning process. To the learning process went smoothly; it was necessary to use a number of strategies to involve students in this type of activity in the classroom:

- The teacher must be aware the latest trends, modern methods and up-to-date authentic resources –

this is the main requirement for the modern teaching process. The use of complex techniques, various methodologies and a clear understanding of the main differences between inductive and deductive learning - gives a good start.

- Eliminate fear of research, introduce students to examples successful innovation work of previous groups, try to create an atmosphere in which students are actively encouraged to ask questions. Motivate them to complicate their work, look for the origins, thus pushing each other to studying complex topics.

- Motivate students to ask questions. Encourage students who ask difficult and possibly ridiculous questions. It is important to tell students that there are no stupid questions [4].

- Inspire confidence and trust. Consistent encouragement, positive emotions and cooperation with students will ensure that they will be more active in asking questions and exploring them.

- Unite students into groups. Inductive learning is a technology that works well in paired interaction and collaboration. In this case, students can discuss and receive confidence, since the research is no longer seems so difficult to them. Students are not

they are afraid to ask questions to each other as a couple, in a team, they are more open and creative in such a more personalized process. The inductive technique can be used in every component of learning English: grammar, spelling, syntax, vocabulary, pronunciation [4].

Options for conducting inductive classes using a traditional and modern inductive learning approach.

Traditional approach:

If the topic of conditional sentences is being studied, using the example of the second conditional and ways of using it, then the exercise might look like this way:

Ask students a few sample questions using the form second conditional sentence:

"If you saw a fire in someone's home, what would you do?"

And they would offer a simple affirmative sentence using the same design

"If I won the lottery, I would donate the money to the Domestic animals Protection Fund."

It is known that the construction structure the second conditional looks like

like this: “if + past simple + would/might + infinitive”. But we can't give it away yet rule for students!)

Questions can be printed on the working sheets so that students can see or ask orally. To guide students in this direction, you can use a few guiding questions:

“Which sentences apply to a real or hypothetical situation?”

"Do the questions refer to something that hypothetically happened in the past, or to something that hypothetically will happen in future?"

"What are the differences between the questions?"

"What are the similarities?"

I hope you will conclude that this structure is used when talking about hypothetical situations in the future or about an unlikely, imaginary situation. The teacher must feel confidently telling the rule in his conventional form only after it is certain that students have achieved a natural understanding of this conditional offers.

Next, you need to continue, rearranging the following aspects and features of the topic and encouraging students to further practice.

Modern approach:

This is a great way to present modern and relevant classes for the modern learner. Thanks to understanding a certain rules or grammatical structure of favorite TV series or song, many students experience a moment of surprise, recognizing and appreciating linguistic elements in such context and form. "Does the singer Beyoncé use the second conditional mood in his song “If I Were a Boy?”

Did the king Charles III really use in his speech at the ceremony coronation second conditional, letting you listen and analyze it speech And so on, there is no limit to your creativity and modern free available authentic resources. The case is solved, the design is found in context.

By making sure your group of students is engaged and using their own reasoning, analysis, teacher proper teaching with this inductive teaching method thus motivating the next group talking detectives and English experts. The inductive method has a huge potential in modern educational world, the ability to ask questions, find independent answers, analyze are the main criteria for developed and educated person. Application of these skills in various areas of education and life increases opportunities student in both professional and interpersonal spheres of communication and development. Teaching this technique is stimulating factor of 6.cognitive the development of the individual as a whole from which a well-rounded personality with developed mental abilities grows.

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